

NFDI4Earth

Report

Learning more about Earth System Sciences users II

Results of an onsite Faculty Day Workshop and online NFDI4Earth Academy Coffee Lecture on discovery, publication, and RDM challenges

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Executive Summary

User engagement is essential for a project such as NFDI4Earth, which aims, among other goals, to promote FAIR and open data practices within the Earth System Sciences (ESS). This report summarizes two community-oriented events designed to gather feedback and strengthen exchange.

The NFDI4Earth Academy organizes free and open online Coffee Lectures on key topics in Research Data Management (RDM) in the ESS. Although primarily targeted at Academy Fellows, these sessions are open to the wider community. The February Coffee Lecture in 2025 included a presentation of the NFDI4Earth OneStop4All portal and invited participants to share their perspectives and experiences.

In addition, a Faculty Day Workshop in 2025 brought together members of the environmental faculty at TU Dresden. With a broader thematic scope, the local NFDI team presented its work packages, covering topics such as governmental data, the OneStop4All portal, the NFDI4Earth Commitment, and the NFDI Basic Services, and engaged participants in a discussion.

The OneStop4All serves as a central access point for resources in the ESS and for services developed within NFDI4Earth. Designed through a user-centered development process, the portal evolves through iterative feedback loops involving diverse stakeholders.

These events form a part of the NFDI4Earth work program's ongoing feedback and landscaping activities. Participants contributed insights into key RDM challenges and needs, providing valuable input for the further development of core services, such as the OneStop4All, as well as community-driven initiatives like the Commitment, while also informing broader strategic activities within NFDI4Earth.

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Introduction

The Faculty of Environmental Sciences¹ of TU Dresden brings together the three environment-related departments of Forest Sciences, Geosciences, and Hydrosociences and several disciplinary chairs within a single organizational framework. Its strong interdisciplinary and international orientation fosters outstanding synergies in both research and teaching. Core research areas include the monitoring and modelling of the Earth system at global, regional, and local scales, as well as research on the sustainable development of the anthroposphere. Each year, the faculty invites its members, staff, and students to a faculty-wide event that encourages dialogue across disciplines and career stages. On the occasion of Faculty Day 2025 (21 May), the TU Dresden Geoinformatics (TUD-GI) and Meteorology (TUD-Met) NFDI team organized a two-hour in-person workshop on NFDI4Earth² and Base4NFDI³, specifically targeting early-career researchers and graduate students.

The workshop included presentations on NFDI activities related to TUD-GI and TUD-Met, with a particular focus on NFDI4Earth's Central Services, the NFDI4Earth FAIRness and Openness Commitment, ongoing activities related to governmental data, as well as approaches and cross-cutting services developed within Base4NFDI.

The NFDI4Earth service OneStop4All⁴ serves as a central access point for key resources of the ESS community and other services developed within NFDI4Earth. The OneStop4All is being developed incrementally following a user-centered design approach that incorporates multiple feedback loops to actively engage diverse stakeholder groups. To support this process, the NFDI4Earth work program includes activities aimed at systematically collecting user needs and feedback.

As the current version of the OneStop4All emphasizes discovery, we organised events which provided opportunities to gather insights on where attendees search for and publish their datasets, and software. Building on these events, this information will help to ensure that the OneStop4All portal integrates relevant repositories, either in the repository search, the repository finding wizard, or by harvesting repositories as data sources for the Knowledge Hub, thereby supporting dataset discovery within the portal.

One of these events was a Coffee Lecture including a live demonstration and poll⁵, held as online event in February 2025. Following on this event, we organized an

¹ https://tu-dresden.de/bu/umwelt?set_language=en

² <https://nfdi4earth.de>

³ <https://base4nfdi.de>

⁴ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16881837>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15227869>

onsite Faculty Day workshop, addressing the same questions with different participants. About 20 attendees were asked to share their perspectives on the most pressing RDM topics and challenges they face. In this report, we describe the Faculty Day workshop results and provide a synthesis of both events.

Where do you search or publish datasets?

The question regarding where attendees search for or publish datasets was designed as an open-ended question. Participants were first asked to write their responses on individual cards and subsequently elaborate on their experiences during the follow-up discussion.

The Coffee Lecture results are provided in the corresponding report⁶. The attendees of the Faculty Day workshop provided the following responses⁷:

Submission order	Original responses (<i>English translation</i>)
1	Zenodo
2	GOVDATA
3	Zenodo
4	umwelt.info
5	Copernicus
6	ESA Sentinel Hub
7	OPARA
8	Unidata repository
9	Zenodo
10	Carbon Portal
11	European Fluxes Data Base
12	Link aus der Publikation (link from publications)
13	Journal publication
14	Dataset on a repository belonging to a test station
15	Rarely thus far
16	Journal with peer-review as stand-alone paper
17	Behörden, (GeoSN) (<i>authorities, (GeoSN)</i>)
18	Hauptsächlich Landesdatenbanken (<i>mainly state databases</i>)
19	Destatis
20	FEDA Forschungs(meta)datenbank (über Service) (<i>FEDA research (meta)database (via service)</i>)

Table 1: Original responses to the question: “Where do you search or publish datasets?” ordered by attendees as submitted during the workshop

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15227869>

⁷ As the workshop was held in mixed language mode, the participants were asked to answer in their preferred language.

The two groups differ in their data discovery and publication habits (Table 2). Coffee Lecture participants are more likely to use disciplinary repositories (such as PANGAEA⁸) and data discovery tools (such as re3data⁹), suggesting a stronger focus on open science and data sharing. Workshop participants seemed to be more engaged with national, governmental, and specialized data portals, indicating practical, applied research and closer ties to institutional or policy-relevant data.

However, participants of both the Coffee Lecture and the workshop formed relatively small groups, we cannot perform a statistical analysis of the results and instead focus on selected key findings as both groups included the NFDI4Earth target group of ESS researchers. Table 2 provides an overview of the responses, revealing a diverse yet structured landscape of data discovery and publication practices among researchers.

According to observations by the workshop organizers, early-career participants, primarily students attending the in-person workshop, formed a distinct subgroup in their responses, indicating they are still developing experience in data publication. Their choices were shaped by tools introduced during their studies or commonly used within their research or study groups, indicating that familiarity and institutional exposure play a relevant role in shaping early data management habits.

In summarizing the broader findings, researchers frequently rely on a combination of widely accessible, discipline-specific, and multidisciplinary platforms. Zenodo¹⁰ emerged as a widely used general-purpose repository for both data discovery and publication. Disciplinary services such as ESA Sentinel Hub¹¹ are used for Earth observation data, while multidisciplinary platforms, such as GOVDATA¹² and Destatis¹³, serve as known sources for national and policy-relevant datasets. Institutional repositories, such as TU Dresden's OPARA¹⁴, are also utilized, underscoring the importance of local infrastructure in supporting research data management. Follow-up discussions further revealed that Google remains a common starting point for data discovery, highlighting potentially ongoing challenges related to data discoverability and metadata quality.

⁸ <https://www.pangaea.de>

⁹ <https://www.re3data.org>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org>

¹¹ <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/analyse/apis/sentinel-hub>

¹² <https://www.govdata.de>

¹³ https://www.destatis.de/DE/Home/_inhalt.html

¹⁴ <https://opara.zih.tu-dresden.de/home>

Platform / Services	OneStop4All Coffee Lecture	Faculty Day Workshop	Total
PANGAEA	4	0	4
Zenodo	3	3	6
Institutional repository	2	1	3
Copernicus	1	1	2
re3data	2	0	2
GOVDATA	0	1	1
umwelt.info	0	1	1
Destatis	0	1	1
FEDA	0	1	1
Carbon Portal	0	1	1
European Fluxes Data Base	0	1	1
Unidata Repository	0	1	1
Journal Publications	0	2	2
Governmental portals & national databases	0	2	2
Earth Data Portal	1	0	1
Earth Data Repository	1	0	1
GFZ Data Services	1	0	1
World Data Center	1	0	1
Google	1	0	1

Table 2: Summarized results about where to search or publish datasets, ordered by the Coffee Lecture and Workshop

Where do you publish software?

The question on where the attendees publish software was implemented in a manner similar to the previous question. The attendees provided the following summarized responses:

Responses	Number of answers
GitHub	4
Zenodo	1
Software publication papers	1
I don't publish software	3

Table 3: Responses given by the workshop participants to the question: "Where do you publish software?"

Following an in-depth discussion on widely used and well-established platforms for data discovery and publication, the workshop participants were largely hesitant regarding software publication. Most indicated that software publication is not perceived as relevant to their research, with only a small number indicating familiarity with or participation in this practice (Table 3).

Nonetheless, key insights were identified from the synthesis of the Coffee Lecture and workshop results (Figure 1). Several platforms were repeatedly mentioned for software sharing, highlighting emerging best practices. The majority of participants reported publishing their developed software on GitHub or GitLab, with many also using Zenodo, often in conjunction with or as a complementary service, primarily to ensure long-term preservation and to obtain persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs). Some researchers rely on institutional repositories or internal Git services, indicating that a portion of software remains unpublished or accessible only within institutional boundaries.

These findings indicate a growing trend toward openly shared and citable software, particularly via widely adopted platforms. However, they also highlight persistent challenges in the broader adoption of software publication practices within the ESS research community, as well as technical challenges related to cross-platform discovery.

Figure 1: Responses about where to publish software, summarized for the Coffee Lecture and Workshop; all participants were able to name various options

Which RDM topics are relevant to your research?

The question on relevant RDM topics was implemented as open question. Again, we summarize the Coffee Lecture and Workshop results. The attendees provided the following original responses:

Submission order	Original responses (<i>English translation</i>)
1	Search, view and download geoscience datasets. where and how to publish dataset compilations belonging to a project
2	FAIR principles
3	metadata schematic
4	selecting a repo for our data, I don't know where to find a suitable one
5	Data curation, Metadata standardization
6	FAIR Data, Open source, data integration of different sources across research domains
7	OSF
8	data provenance and metadata scheme
9	e.g. Harmonized Metadata, Publication of large datasets, ...
10	reproducibility of workflows/code how to license own published datasets

Submission order	Original responses (<i>English translation</i>)
11	To give researchers such RDM tasks that they also can fulfil in terms of skills and in terms to the tools and infrastructure we provide to them.
12	quality and integrity
13	storage
14	all topics along the data - lifecycle
15	publishing, searching and finding data(sets), meta-data
16 *	Reusability
17 *	Accessibility, Transparency, Reusability
18 *	Reusability
19 *	Data Management Plan
20 *	Raumbezug der Daten muss konsistent sein (<i>The spatial reference of the data must be consistent.</i>)
21 *	Datenformat, Versionskompatibilität (<i>data formats, version compatibility</i>)
22 *	Vereinheitlichung, Zusammenschluss von Portalen (<i>Harmonisation, aggregation of portals</i>)
23 *	Einheitliche umfassende Verfügbarkeit von Daten verschiedener Institutionen, z.B. Städte, Bundesländer (<i>Consistent and comprehensive availability of data across different institutions, e.g., cities and federal states</i>)
24 *	Verständliche Struktur & Dokumentation, Meta-Daten (<i>Clear structure and documentation, metadata</i>)
25 *	Data archive, compilation (+ integrat.) of multiple PhD projects
26 *	Die Datenmenge (<i>The amount of data</i>)
27 *	Räumlich hoch aufgelöste Geodaten bundesweit ! (<i>Nationwide high-resolution geospatial data!</i>)
28 *	Lizenz-Problem (<i>license problem</i>)
29 *	Umgang mit qualitativem Thema für Forschungsdaten (Interviewdaten als Datenmanagement? Einzelfallstudie)? (<i>Handling qualitative research data (e.g., interview data as data management or case study?)</i>)
30 *	Establishing a workflow management in the daily routine
31 *	Neues Feld (new field of work)

Table 4: Original responses to the question: "Which RDM topics are relevant to your research?", ordered by the Coffee Lecture and Workshop (the latter marked with *)

Summary

In general, the responses show that researchers continue to encounter challenges throughout the entire data lifecycle and that the group of ESS researchers vary widely in their data search habits and RDM experiences.

The findings point to a clear demand for improved support, both human-based (through experts and support structures) and automated, in selecting appropriate repositories and more effective search mechanisms. Several relevant features are already available within the OneStop4All, such as a repository wizard and data search functionalities. However, systematic usability testing is needed to ensure these tools are fully aligned with researchers' practical requirements (and corresponding data products).

Overall, the results underscore the ongoing need for better tools, clearer guidance, and stronger institutional or openly available support for effective disciplinary RDM or, at the very least, improved discoverability of existing resources. Addressing these gaps will be essential to enhance the accessibility, reusability, quality, and usability of research data and software across disciplines. By building on these insights and fostering collaboration across the community, NFDI4Earth, in its role as a German ESS community and provider network, is well positioned to advance toward a more usable, integrated, accessible, reusable, and sustainable research data ecosystem.